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Abstract

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable outlines the communication and outreach strategy for EOSC4Cancer. It lays out an action plan for the consortium partners, aimed at making the project goals and progress well understood by all relevant target groups. Specific objectives to achieve this aim are:

- ▶ Awareness raising: raise awareness about the cancer data structure being developed by the project within EOSC
- ▶ Engagement of key stakeholders: offer a structure for diverse stakeholders to be informed about and contribute to the project's work (see target audiences in chapter 4.2)
- ▶ Scientific publications, participations in conferences and events: include EOSC4Cancer research results into academic body of knowledge through publications and presentations
- ▶ Facilitation of post-project adoption of EOSC4Cancer: make project results available for end user groups.

Apart from the specific cancer-data related contents, the strategy also aims to inform how the EOSC infrastructure functions in this context. A visual identity that relies on the EOSC co-branding guidelines strengthens this brand recognition and is also applied in related project templates.

To ensure we consider the relevant stakeholders for a cancer data ecosystem within EOSC, we stratify their roles from two perspectives: position within the cancer research universe and role within the EOSC ecosystem. Also, stakeholders in synergistic projects represent an important target group.

EOSC4Cancer uses different channels to reach its diverse target groups:

- ▶ Project website
- ▶ Social media channels
- ▶ Scientific publications
- ▶ Project events
- ▶ Newsletter

This strategy is enabled by the Virtual Communication Office Team – an organisational structure consisting in regular meetings of communication professionals within the WP6 partners.

WP6 employs different tools to achieve its communication and outreach goals, such as a planning tool for external events participation, social media tracking and newsletter sending tools.

Precise communication and outreach key performance indicators are defined in this report and will be monitored throughout the project duration.

1 Introduction

This chapter gives an overview of the document scope, target audience and structure.

1.1 Scope and objectives of the deliverable

This deliverable presents EOSC4Cancer's strategy to promote the project and to reach out to relevant stakeholders. It sets out an action plan to be implemented by the consortium partners, led by work package (WP) 6 leader, EMPIRICA.

This deliverable has the specific objectives to:

- ▶ Define dissemination and communication goals
- ▶ Describe the target audiences to which the dissemination and communication activities are directed
- ▶ Set out a dissemination and communication action plan concerning progress and results of the project
- ▶ Present the respective dissemination and communication channels, tools and organisation structures
- ▶ Choose metrics to track monitor the action plan's progress.

1.2 Structure of the document

This document is structured in five main sections. After an introduction to the document (Chapter 1), the second section outlines the communication and outreach strategy (Chapter 1.3). The third section describes the communication and dissemination channels (Chapter 3), while the concrete structures and tools used are outlined in the fourth section (Chapter 4). Finally, the last section (Chapter 5) sets out concrete monitoring and reporting targets.

1.3 Intended audience

The deliverable is directed at the EOSC4Cancer consortium partners, as well as the wider EOSC community.

2 Outreach and communication strategy

This chapter elaborates on the concrete strategy to reach out to stakeholders and communicate EOSC4Cancers key messages. We firstly describe the communication goals and objectives before exploring the stakeholder groups the project aims to reach.

2.1 Goals and objectives

EOSC4Cancer is a project within the European Open Science Cloud – an ecosystem that has been established by the European Commission since 2015 and implemented in two phases, through a series of calls under Horizon 2020 (2018-2020) and the EOSC European co-programmed partnership / Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (2021-2030). EOSC's overall goal is to make available to researchers, innovators, companies, and citizens in Europe “a federated and open multi-disciplinary environment where they can publish, find and reuse data, tools and services for research, innovation and educational purposes”.¹

EOSC4Cancer is part of the second phase, which follows a “more stakeholder-driven approach with a shared vision, common objectives and complementary contributions at European, national and institutional levels”². Its overall objective is to prepare EOSC services for cancer research and enrich EOSC with data, tools and services from the cancer community. EOSC services will be used to build a structure that joins cancer centres, research infrastructures, leading research groups, major computational infrastructure across Europe, and other relevant stakeholders. This structure aims to enable the exploitation of cancer data beyond the current level.

Thus, this communication and outreach activity aims to make these goals understandable to the target audience, highlighting methods EOSC4Cancer deploys to this aim.

This entails the following aspects:

- ▶ EOSC4Cancer’s goals:
 - ▶ Enable storage, sharing, access, analysis and processing of research data and other digital research objects from basic and clinical cancer research
 - ▶ Mobilise, interconnect and interoperate datasets relevant in cancer research
 - ▶ Make cancer research data and analysis systems easily accessible to basic and clinical scientists in the most used cancer analysis portals
 - ▶ Integrate digital tools, data analytics and Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning tools for the analysis of cancer data in the cancer analysis portals
 - ▶ Contribute to the European Health Data Space (EHDS), the Horizon Europe European Open Science, Cloud (EOSC) Partnership and the Cancer Mission.
- ▶ EOSC4Cancer’s progress, such as:
 - ▶ Project milestones
 - ▶ Events
 - ▶ Key deliverables
- ▶ EOSC4Cancer’s outcomes, such as:
 - ▶ Representative and prospective data sets (M6, 18)
 - ▶ Reference installation of XNAT (M21)
 - ▶ Inclusion of novel datatypes in cBioPortal (M21)
 - ▶ Roadmap for a European Cancer Data Space (M30)

¹ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science/european-open-science-cloud-eosc_en

² https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science/european-open-science-cloud-eosc_en

- ▶ Outcomes related to the five use cases.
- ▶ Embedment into European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) environment:
 - Ambition to develop a “web of FAIR data and services”.
 - Federated system approach; building on top of existing infrastructures by EC, Member States, research communities.

With this background, specific communication and dissemination objectives are the following:

1. Awareness raising: raise awareness of the cancer data structure within EOSC that the project is creating
2. Engagement of key stakeholders: offer a structure for diverse stakeholders to be informed about and contribute to the project work (see target audiences in chapter 2.2)
3. Scientific publications, participations in conferences and events: include EOSC4Cancer research results into academic body of knowledge through publications and presentations.
4. Facilitation of post-project adoption of EOSC4Cancer: make available project results for end user groups.

The following chapter outline in more detail the target groups and the methods used to achieve these goals.

2.2 Targeted audiences and stakeholder mapping

This chapter outlines the target audience of EOSC4Cancer’s outreach and communication activities, stratified into different stakeholder groups.

2.2.1 Relevant stakeholder groups

WP6 lead EMPIRICA has listed stakeholder groups that are relevant for the communication and outreach strategy.

Stakeholder group	Relevance
General public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Tax-payers financing research and healthcare ▶ Multipliers in building trust in cancer data exchange
Patient and survivor associations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Target group directly affected by cancer ▶ Owners and generators of cancer data ▶ Interested in a more efficient patient journey
Cancer researchers (academia and industry)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Generators of cancer data through research and clinical trials ▶ Users of cancer data for research, drug development etc. ▶ Educators of future researchers, healthcare and industry professionals ▶ Potential creators of AI/ML models ▶ Producers of devices used to collect real world cancer data
Cancer clinical scientists	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Contributing cancer data knowledge both from patient care and basic research ▶ Catalysts for the uptake of cancer research in clinical practice
Cancer experts in hospitals and tumour boards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Provide interdisciplinary view on cancer ▶ Familiar with diverse types of cancer data
Infrastructure operators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Creating IT infrastructures for cancer data storage and processing

Stakeholder group	Relevance
Decision- and policy-maker	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Users of health data for public health policy ▶ Decision-makers on central regulations (e.g. data protection, healthcare regulations)
Public health authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Procurers of healthcare
Funder/payer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Reimbursors of healthcare ▶ Users of cancer data in reimbursement processes
Stakeholders building/implementing EOSC and EHDS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Contributors to infrastructure aspects ▶ Facilitator to engage with overall EOSC community
Synergy EU projects and cancer initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Creators of outcomes that are relevant for EOSC4Cancer (e.g. different use cases and data types, interoperability achievements, insights on genomics) ▶ Hosts of already existing knowledgeable expert and stakeholder communities ▶ Potential users of EOSC4Cancer's data sets and infrastructures

Table 1 List of Key Stakeholders

The project consortium is aware that some stakeholders who might be crucial for disruptive innovation, such as health insurances and payment schemes, regulatory authorities, or patient organisations, may not be aware of or interested in developments in EOSC4Cancer. Thus, one goal of the communication and outreach strategy is to point out the value of well-curated cancer data sets within the EOSC infrastructure to these groups.

2.2.2 Stakeholder stratification

These stakeholders can be grouped into different categories, to better understand the different views and expectations. This is crucial to derive appropriate communication strategy: key messages, channels chosen, topic selection.

Stratification according to EOSC ecosystem roles

Within the EOSC universe, the Digital Skills for FAIR and Open Science Report³ by the EOSC Executive Board Skills and Training Working Group defines different roles. While WP5 will align the Cancer Data Actors and their skills and training needs in a more detailed manner, the table below presents the EOSC Ecosystem roles as defined in the report and provides tentative examples from within EOSC4Cancer.

EOSC Ecosystem Role	Description	Examples in EOSC4Cancer
Researcher	Main focus of the EOSC ecosystem, accessing it to obtain, process, create, store and share research data.	Cancer researchers: would browse EOSC4Cancer data sets to carry out a study
EOSC Enabler	Researcher with both profound domain knowledge and open science and FAIR skills, able to	Cancer researchers with technical skills who integrates genomic data processing suite into

³ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/af7f7807-6ce1-11eb-aeb5-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-190694287>

EOSC Ecosystem Role	Description	Examples in EO SC4Cancer
	design discipline-specific applications with EO SC services and data. Acting as a bridge between scientific community and technical services.	EO SC4Cancer infrastructure (e.g. user in open science initiatives like Galaxy, cBioPortal etc.)
Data Scientist/ Data Analyst	Data processing expert who can evaluate data quality and extract and represent relevant knowledge	Data scientist developing a machine learning algorithm for the EO SC4Cancer federated learning infrastructure
Research Software Engineer	IT expert designing, implementing, and maintaining software in the EO SC ecosystem	Software engineer designing software for EO SC4Cancer
Data Research Infrastructure Support Professional	ICT expert managing and operating research infrastructures and services to store, preserve and process research data	Professional managing and operation research infrastructures in EO SC4Cancer
EO SC Educator	Expert organising content and managing training activities in EO SC. Thorough knowledge of the EO SC ecosystem.	EO SC4Cancer training organisers on institutional or national level
Data Curator	Expert managing and overseeing an organisations entire data to ensure compliance and provide users with high quality, accessible data.	Senior level cancer registry representative – e.g. collecting and publishing genomic data samples related to cancer, with geographic annotation, in domain-specific standard formats
Data Steward/ Data Librarian	Expert for preparing and treating data, including selection, storage, preservation, and metadata maintenance.	Expert adding metadata to a genomic dataset related to cancer
Citizen	People interested in science, wishing to contribute to citizen science initiatives.	Citizens, patients, and survivors anonymously sharing cancer data to EO SC4Cancer
Policy Maker	Policy makers extract information from research to build policies or strategic frameworks	Governing board of a public health directorate using EO SC4Cancer data to help implement national cancer task force.

Table 2 List of Stakeholders stratified by EO SC Ecosystem roles

A comparison with the overall EO SC4Cancer stakeholders described above shows that researchers are main targets in both contexts. The categories citizen and policy maker overlap, with the cancer data dimension adding a more specific context. The EO SC- and data-related roles can be found in different institutions, such as research, industry, and funders.

While we will orient the communication and outreach strategy mainly according to the stakeholder groups listed in 2.2.1, the role classifications within the EO SC ecosystem will be valuable to fine tune communication message and objectives for specific sub-categories of stakeholders, such as:

- ▶ Encouraging cancer researchers to become EOSC enablers: e.g. by raising awareness for importance of FAIR data and promoting participation in WP5 training activities
- ▶ Communicating the particularities of cancer data to EOSC enablers and data scientists/analysts without specific cancer knowledge
- ▶ Invite individuals to contribute to EOSC4Cancer infrastructure who act as data curators or stewards/librarians in industry, research or funding institutions: e.g. for clinical trial cancer data
- ▶ Reach out to healthcare professionals to raise awareness on basic FAIR data principles and the fact that they already perform basic data steward functions as routine part of their job
- ▶ Communicate to patients, survivors and citizens that EOSC4Cancer helps provide a secure infrastructure where their donated data can be integrated and will contribute to research
- ▶ Present to policy makers how the well-curated EOSC4Cancer data sets provide high quality data as a basis for decision making
- ▶ Inform funders how EOSC4Cancer's data sets can help contextualise their reimbursement decisions – and how their reimbursement data, in return, can contribute to a European Cancer Data Space.

In this manner, the EOSC ecosystem roles will serve as a basis to engage the most relevant stakeholders with view to the principles of the European Open Science Cloud⁴:

- ▶ Seamless access
- ▶ FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability) management
- ▶ Reliable reuse of research data and all other digital objects produced along the research life cycle (e.g. methods, software and publications)

Synergy cancer projects

Synergy projects and initiatives are of particular importance for EOSC4Cancer. Communication and outreach to them is mainly driven by the aim to present the EOSC4Cancer infrastructure to other cancer projects and avoid research redundancies. It will fulfil the following objectives, among others:

- ▶ Reach out to existing expert and stakeholder communities hosted in other projects
- ▶ Present the EOSC4Cancer use cases to projects focussing on other cancer types
- ▶ Present the EOSC4Cancer data infrastructure to projects creating complementary cancer data infrastructures.

Project	Abstract	Website
UNCAN	To achieve the next breakthrough needed to advance the understanding of cancer mechanisms in order to improve cancer prevention, early diagnosis and treatment, providing a basis for saving millions of European citizens' lives.	https://uncan.eu/
B1MG	CSA to provide best practice, recommendations, and guidance for the deployment of GDI.	https://b1mg-project.eu/

⁴ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science/european-open-science-cloud-eosc_en

Project	Abstract	Website
GDI	To deploy sustainable and secure cross-border linkage of and access to a multitude of genomic and related phenotypic, clinical and other datasets across Europe based on the progress achieved in the context of the 1+ Million Genomes Initiative	https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/
canSERV	canSERV will contribute to the EU Mission Cancer through the provision of cutting-edge interdisciplinary and customised oncology services across the entire cancer continuum to achieve a comprehensive portfolio of oncology-related research infrastructures services available to all EU member- and associated countries	www.canSERV.eu
can.HEAL	To improve access for individuals and cancer patients and survivors to prevention, diagnosis and treatment of cancer through personalised medicine, by upscaling available innovation in the field of innovative cancer diagnosis and treatment (develop guidelines and recommendations to better determine who and what to test, organise health services to implement genetic testing, and provide specific education and training for health workers to advance our understanding of cancer control).	Website under construction (https://www.e-cancer.be/fr/projects/canheal-building-eu-cancer-and-public-health-genomics-action-grants-cancer-diagnostic-and)
EUCAIM	The aim of the European Cancer Imaging Initiative is to foster innovation and deployment of digital technologies in cancer treatment and care, to achieve more precise and faster clinical decision-making, diagnostics, treatments and predictive medicine for cancer patients.	Website to be launched (https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/cancer-imaging)
GerSom	This project is a multicentric study that includes 17 IRCCS (Italian Institutes for comprehensive cancer patient care and research) and aims to demonstrate the feasibility of a joint diagnostic path at the time of diagnosis of cancer for the identification of altered genes in tumours (for prognostic and therapy response definition purposes) and CPGs in the germline (for mapping cancer genetic risk). ACC has developed and validated a cost-effective gene panel that can be run quickly (<1 week) to analyze 467 altered tumour genes, including 172 CPGs. 4,000 patients with a genetic predisposition to develop tumours will be recruited.	https://www.alleanzacontroilcancro.it/en/progetti/gersom/
Health Big Data	The ten-year HBD project, coordinated by the Italian Ministry of Health, involves 51 IRCCS (Italian Institutes for comprehensive cancer patient care and research) and entails the creation or enhancement of local and centralized IT platforms to ensure extraction, integration and interoperability of clinical and scientific data. The type of data that will be collected and shared is heterogeneous and includes omics data (genomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, metabolomics), clinical data (electronic medical record and patient follow-up data), clinical imaging and radiomics data; and data provided by the patient. Data from biosensors, environmental, social, and economic data will also be included in the medium term.	https://www.alleanzacontroilcancro.it/en/progetti/health-big-data/

Project	Abstract	Website
HealthyCloud	HealthyCloud is funded by Horizon 2020 innovation and research programme. This project aims to generate a ready-to-implement Roadmap that consists of guidelines, recommendations and specifications that will enable the distribution of health research across Europe. This roadmap together with the feedback gathered from a broad range of stakeholders will be the basis to produce the final HealthyCloud Strategic Agenda for the European Health Research and Innovation Cloud (HRIC). The goal of HealthyCloud is to optimize the advances in health and biomedical research by providing efficient and timely access to health data to support transnational, clinical epidemiological-population level research. The project is comprised of 21 partners that are vested in state-of-the-art biomedical research and is geared towards adopting best practices on how to efficiently manage health data.	https://healthycloud.eu/
EUCANCan	European-Canadian Cancer network is a four-year project funded by the Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Canadian Institutes of health and research. The goal of EUCANCan is to implement a new technological, cultural, and legal integrated framework to improve modern oncology and facilitate the efficient analysis, management and sharing of cancer genomic data. This framework, while contributing to improving biomedical cancer research, also aims at serving as a model for globalizing and enriching personalized medicine initiatives by allowing exchange of data across multiple national health systems.	https://eucancan.com/
AACR GENIE	AACR Project GENIE is a publicly accessible cancer registry of real-world clinic-genomic data assembled through data sharing between 19 leading international cancer centers. Through the efforts of strategic partners Sage Bionetworks and cBioPortal, the registry aggregates, harmonizes, and links clinical-grade, next-generation cancer genomic sequencing data with clinical outcomes obtained during routine medical practice from nearly every cancer patient treated at these institutions. The consortium and its activities are driven by openness, transparency, and inclusion, ensuring that the project output remains accessible to the global cancer research community for the benefit of all.	https://www.aacr.org/professionals/research/aacr-project-genie

Table 3 Indicative List of EOSC4Cancer synergy projects

As part of its stakeholder engagement and multi-stakeholder forum in Task 6.2, EOSC4Cancer will also be attentive to its synergy projects and initiatives' communication and participate in their outreach activities.

3 Outreach and communication channels

This chapter outlines the channels EOSC4Cancer leverages for its communication and outreach, starting with its visual identity (chapter 3.1), describing the project website (chapter 3.2), social media channels (chapter 3.3), project events (chapter 0) and newsletter (3.6).

3.1 Logo, style guide and project templates

The visual strategy for the dissemination campaign adheres to the Co-branding guidelines for Horizon Europe INFRAEOSC projects⁵, as proposed by the EOSC Association. The documents outline the main and alternate colour schemes, typeface, logo usage, and the inclusion of the EU emblem for consistency in all campaign communications.

This comprehensive guidebook outlines the proper way to use the recently introduced EOSC logo. It covers all aspects of the logo's usage, including the selection of main and alternative colours to ensure optimal visibility. The choice of different colours ensures that the logo used provides maximum visibility. Clear and concise instructions are provided to help users make the most of this important visual representation.

Figure 1 EOSC4Cancer standard

An internal EOSC4Cancer logo was created according to these co-branding guidelines in M1 of the project, before the kick-off meeting. An accompanying design manual applies the guidelines to EOSC4Cancer, illustrating the EOSC4Cancer logo versions and its different use cases.

Horizontal

On white background – standard

On light coloured background – all black

On black background – White font
(don't copy the background)

On dark coloured background – all white
(don't copy the background)

Figure 2 Excerpt from EOSC4Cancer design manual

⁵ https://www.eosc.eu/sites/default/files/2022-09/EOSC%20Co-Branding%20Guidelines%20for%20HE%20INFRAEOSC%20Projects_HR.pdf

In accordance with these EOSC4Cancer colour scheme and logo, a set of Microsoft Word and PowerPoint templates was created for deliverables, other project documents and project presentations.

3.2 Project website

This section describes the outline, management, and genesis of the project website, located

Figure 3 Screenshots from selected project templates

at <https://eosc4cancer.eu>.

3.2.1 Website objective and target audience

The EOSC4Cancer website is tailored to researchers and educational organizations. Its primary goal is to increase awareness of the project's progress and serve as a source of information for stakeholders interested in learning more about the project. The website targets the research community as its primary audience, but affiliated entities and other participants can also benefit by staying informed about the project's progress through regular updates.

3.2.2 Structure and contents

Landing page

The landing page of a website serves as the initial point of contact for visitors, providing them with a comprehensive overview of the project and its offerings. It features a user-friendly navigation menu with tabs for information about the project, its use cases, recent news and events, and technical work packages.

Figure 4 Project Website landing page on February 13 2023

The design of the landing page is intuitive and easy to navigate, with clear headlines and a direct link to the project's social media as well as newsletter subscription page for regular updates and engagement.

Project timeline

Figure 5 Project Timeline as displayed on February 13th

The page also includes a project timeline to showcase the progress of the project and its achievements.

About

The 'About' section has four subheadings for information on 'The Project', the 'Consortium', the 'Synergy Projects' and the 'European Open Science Cloud'. 'The Project' outlines the main objective of EOSC4Cancer is to make diverse types of cancer data accessible and interoperable across national boundaries through federated systems, and to offer them via community-driven analysis environments in order to support the European Cancer Mission and accelerate progress in cancer research.

The 'Consortium' page states the parties and affiliated entities involved from 13 different countries. The 'Synergy Project' lists all the project EOSC4Cancer is searching for synergies with.

Figure 6 Presentation of "About" menu on website

Use Cases

The five cases used for this project are preventing cancer by identifying risks linking environmental data to cancer registry data, data-based optimization of cancer screening, data-based treatment of localized tumours, data-based treatment of localised tumours specifically improving the treatment of colorectal cancer and connecting omics data from multiple sources to a Clinical Decision Support system to facilitate clinical decisions.

Figure 7 Presentation of Uses Cases on website

News and Events

The news page on the website features updates on the project in chronological order, including information on the project start, kick-off meeting and social media presence.

Technical Workpackages

The section of technical work packages provides information about the technical infrastructure that interconnects the five use cases by receiving data input and ensuring data flow structures for the European Open Science Cloud for Cancer, which includes Federated data spaces, distributed harmonization efforts, and Federated cancer data analysis through portals across Europe.

TECHNICAL WORKPACKAGES ▾

Federated cancer data analysis
Distributed harmonisation efforts
Federated data spaces

Figure 8 Presentation of Technical WPs on Website

Newsletter sign-up

Website visitors could also subscribe for a newsletter via email and receive regular updates and relevant information. Newsletters are a great way to build a community by keeping subscribers informed and engaged.

Subscribe to our newsletter

Stay up to date on EOSC4Cancer's progress by signing up to our newsletter!

Firstname*

Lastname*

E-Mail*

Yes, I want to subscribe to the newsletter.

Figure 9 Newsletter subscription form on website

3.2.3 Maintenance and evolution

EMPIRICA is responsible for the maintenance of the website, and we are dedicated to ensuring that it is always up-to-date and functioning smoothly. In the future, we plan to offer an option to download valuable resources for example a section for the download of important deliverables. This way, the website will provide a centralized location for all viewers, clients, or

any interested party, to easily access and utilise the materials they require for their respective needs.

3.3 Social media channels

The following chapter presents EOSC4Cancers social media channels and planned communication campaigns.

3.3.1 Rationale

By leveraging the power of social media, the idea is to reach a wider audience to make them aware of the various initiatives and efforts made by EOSC4Cancer. This transfers the consortium messages during the stages of the project using eye-catching graphics, compelling posts, and engaging content. Doing so will get as many people involved as possible by pointing them back to the project website as well. Furthermore, this would enable the target to connect with other EU cancer-related projects by sharing their contents on the EOSC4Cancer channels.

3.3.2 Target audience

The social media presence is specifically tailored to the target audiences outlined in chapter 2.2. By focusing on this specific group, especially those in the cancer field, the aim is to harness their expertise and feedback on various aspects of the projects. Social media also provides a platform for individuals and organisations to share their personal experiences and perspectives and is thus complementary to academic publications.

3.3.3 Status Quo

Project accounts have been created on three social media channels: namely, LinkedIn, Twitter, and Mastodon at the start of the project. All partners are involved in these accounts to frequently share the consortium activities and the key outcomes achieved.

Platform	Account Name	URL	Followers (as of 27 February 2023)
LinkedIn	EOSC4Cancer	https://www.linkedin.com/company/eosc4cancer/	272
Twitter	EOSC4Cancer	https://twitter.com/EOSC4Cancer	207
Mastodon	EOSC4Cancer	https://eupolicy.social/@eosc4cancer	10

Table 4 EOSC4Cancer social media accounts

As the project targets specific types of audiences, these three platforms have been chosen. They have wide range of accounts of research and medical professionals. Moreover, many cancer-related projects are disseminating their activities on them, creating a valuable community in the cancer field. LinkedIn is a business and employment-focused social media platform, while Twitter and, Mastodon, are more casual platform that also contain nonprofessional accounts.

LinkedIn

As part of the promotion campaign, the LinkedIn account has been consistently sharing updates on the project's progress, initiatives, and events. This started with an introductory post about the project mentioning all the partners and the affiliated entities. Then continued posting and reposting about the meetings the consortium did, the project website and its content and supporting other synergy projects and cancer-related ones. The posts contained hashtags

Figure 10 Screenshots of LinkedIn profile and exemplary post

referring to cancer data, EO SC and other EU cancer projects to enable cross-referencing of content by topic or theme. The account has a growing network of 272 followers as of 27.02.2023 and has received positive engagement on various posts reflecting the impact of the project. In addition to reporting on project developments, the posts are aligned with relevant current medical events.

Twitter

Similarly, the Twitter account has promoted initiatives and posted updates on webinars, surveys etc. Moreover, since Twitter is a more casual platform, more individuals affiliated with the partners are more active on it and shared more content related to the project. Much of the content has been shared on the project's account besides sharing relevant tweets from the active account of the EO SC Association. A selection of recent tweets has been added here as an example.

Figure 11 Screenshots of Twitter profile and exemplary posts

Mastodon

In response to recent changes regarding Twitter, it was decided to follow in footsteps of our peers and establish a presence on Mastodon. This decentralised, open-source social network offers a secure platform for sharing updates on the project and engaging with its audience.

We created the account on 22.02.2023 on the “eupolicy.social” instance, which is one of the bubbles Mastodon has. The aim of these bubbles is to gather projects and persons with the same interest in one bubble. “eupolicy.social” bubble is for EU policy and where many other EU projects accounts have been created. Followers and following accounts have been imported from Twitter using Debirdify⁶ and Fedifinder⁷ websites.

Our followers on LinkedIn and Twitter have been notified about our availability on Mastodon. Then, a welcoming post and a post about the WP3 workshop were the first two posts on our page. However, we plan to keep the followers updated about the upcoming achievements and milestones.

Figure 12 Screenshots of Mastodon profile and exemplary posts

3.3.4 Social media campaigns

During the lifetime of the project, social media will be used as a key distributor of the project messages. Therefore, key project milestones and planned events will be published through social media campaigns. The two causes behind this are to get the targeted community involved and to present what the project achieved in every stage.

A social media campaign varies from routine updating on the status of the project since partners are given extensive materials to utilize as the basis for their own postings, as opposed to only reposting content from the official project accounts.

Early preparation of a campaign’s theme and key messages is essential. When a work package’s major outcome is the focus of a campaign, the WP6 team first meets with the work package leader to go over the specifics of the campaign. The campaign aspects that must be agreed upon include ideas for social media postings (tweets for Twitter, core message for LinkedIn), supporting visuals, and occasionally an overall press release. Then, a package with guidelines and instructions about the campaign’s timing, goal, and material use is sent to each

⁶ <https://debirdify.pruvisto.org/>

⁷ <https://fedifinder.glitch.me/>

partner. After the campaign is over, the impact of the campaign is tracked by WP6 team using social media tracking tools.

We drafted potential campaigns in the table below. These campaigns must be approved by each individual WP leader. We chose the topics and timing according to project deliverables and milestones that worth communicating to different stakeholders. We considered time gaps between milestone/deliverable completion and holiday seasons as well.

Campaign No	Theme	Content lead	Month	Status
1	Project Start	EMPIRICA/BSC	1	Completed
2	Website launch	EMPIRICA/BSC	3	Completed
3	Establishment of Stakeholder Forum, Ethics and Advisory Board	EATRIS/ ELIXIR/EBI/EMBL	7	Planned
4	Report on annotation and harmonisation needs	UP	9	Planned
5	Data Access Interoperability	ELIXIR/EBI/EMBL	12	Planned
6	EOSC4Cancer training workshop	EATRIS	15	Planned
7	Virtual research environments interoperable with data portals	BSC	19	Planned
9	Reference Installation of XNAT and Inclusion of novel data types in cBioPortal	EUROBIOIMAGING/ Lygature	22	Planned
10	Draft roadmap published for consultation	Elixir	25	Planned
11	EOSC4Cancer conference	EMPIRICA/BSC	30	Planned

Table 5 Social media campaigns – past and planned

Additional ad hoc communication campaigns will be hosted to disseminate project workshops, such as hackathons, contentathons and connectathons. WP6 will maintain a close collaboration with the content-leading work package and elicit whether they wish an event promotion with a call for action to register. Considering the high level of domain knowledge required for some of the planned events, EOSC4Cancer might prefer hand-selected invitations that are not disclosed on social media. In this case, communication will consist in publishing a posterior news item.

These social media campaigns might also include the promotion of videos – such as short interviews with certification scheme owners when reaching important milestones or video footage of events.

3.4 Scientific publications and targeted media

To contribute to integrate EOSC4Cancers results into the academic body of knowledge, the consortium plans scientific open access, peer reviews publications in high impact journals. In this way, it will also engage scientific media as a (secondary) target group of communication.

Relevant journals to publish in include:

- ▶ European Journal of Cancer
- ▶ JAMA Oncology
- ▶ Cancer Research
- ▶ Cancer
- ▶ Nature Reviews Cancer
- ▶ British Journal of Cancer
- ▶ Genomics
- ▶ Bioinformatics
- ▶ Information Services & Use
- ▶ Health Data Science
- ▶ Journal of Big Data

We will also consider targeting EU news media platforms, as well as their related newsletters. This includes platforms like Futurium, Connect Newsroom - Shaping Europe's Digital Future, EU Health Policy and similar outlets.

3.5 Project events

EOSC4Cancer will both host own events, as well as participate in external events. This will fulfil the double goal of reaching out to stakeholders and participating to the academic body of knowledge.

An initial event to be mentioned in this regard is the synergy meeting co-organised by EOSC4Cancer and UNCAN.eu on 17 January 2023. Together with six other cancer data related projects, they discussed mutual use of different structures created in other initiatives. Likewise, the representatives started to create a catalogue of ongoing EU cancer projects and the methodologies and data they use.

3.5.1 Participation in external events

The project will be represented at relevant events from the cancer data and EOSC community.

The table below presents a tentative overview of possible regular conferences where EOSC4Cancer could be represented:

Event name	Event date 2023	Venue	Type of event	Comments	Website
DMEA 2023	25.04. 2023	Berlin, Germany	Conference and trade show	Europe's leading digital health event, where experts on the digital health industry meet	https://www.dmea.de/en/

Event name	Event date 2023	Venue	Type of event	Comments	Website
				once a year, also offering opportunities for stakeholders	
Vitalis Conference 2023	22.02. 2023	Gothenburg, Sweden	Conference	Vitalis is the largest eHealth event in Scandinavia, yearly attracting attendees with the shared aim of building their knowledge and improving tomorrow's health care.	https://en.vitalis.nu/
European Molecular Imaging Meeting	14.- 17.03. 2023	Salzburg, Austria	Conference	Annual meeting of the European Society for Medical Imaging, bringing together attendees from all fields of imaging sciences	https://e-smi.eu/meetings/emim/emim-2023/
Innovation for Health	06.04. 2023	Rotterdam, Netherlands	Conference	Conference on digital transformation in healthcare	https://www.hyphenprojects.nl/i4h
Elixir Innovation and SME Forum: AI in healthcare	13.04. 2023	Utrecht, Netherlands	Forum, conference	The Innovation and SME Forum is a one-day event that provides the platform for experts from the private and public sector who work on AI in the healthcare sector to discuss challenges and opportunities in health digitalisation and data-driven innovation.	https://elixir-europe.org/events/innovation-sme-forum-ai-health-research
AACR Annual Meeting	14.- 19.04. 2023	Orlando, Florida, USA	Conference	Annual meeting of the American Association for Cancer Research	https://www.aacr.org/meeting/aacr-annual-meeting-2023/
HIMSS23 Europe	7.- 9.06. 2023	Lisbon, Portugal	Conference, Exhibition	Health information and technology conference and exhibition, attracting industry, policy makers and EU projects	https://www.himss.org/event-himss-europe
Radical Health Festival	12.- 15.06. 2023	Helsinki, Finland	Conference	Interdisciplinary digital health conference bringing together	https://radicalhealthfestival.mess

Event name	Event date 2023	Venue	Type of event	Comments	Website
				healthcare, IT, industry and clinicians	ukeskus.com/
Open Science Conference	27.-29.06.2023	Hamburg, Germany	Conference	Annual conference dedicated to open science	https://www.openscience-conference.eu/
Bits and Pretzels HealthTech Conference	29.06.2023	Munich, Germany	Conference, Trade Fair	Bringing together startup companies with investors, med tech, pharma and policy makers	https://www.bitsandpretzels.com/healthtech

Table 6 List of potential conferences to attend

Rationale

The project's strategy includes both organising and participating in a wide range of public events by project partners, from webinars to workshops and conferences. These events are important to reach stakeholders from different areas of Europe. This would enable us to network and engage various types of cancer-interested people holding different perspectives. Moreover, synergies with different EU projects about cancer data research will be gained.

Status quo

The project has been already communicated through presentations and networking in a series of events and webinars:

Campaign No	Title	Co-host	When / Where	Type
1	Synergies with EOESC4Cancer	UNIMAN Stian Soiland-Reyes	28/6/2022 Amsterdam	Collaboration with EU-funded projects
2	EOESC4Cancer: A European-wide foundation to accelerate Data-driven Cancer Research	BSC Salvador Capella	11/10/2022 Universidade do Algarve	conference
3	Horizon Europe projects coordination meeting in the context of the EOESC European Partnership	BSC Alfonso Valencia and Salvador Capella	30/09/2022 Brussels	meeting
4	Cancer Community Workshop Session at GA4GH November Virtual Connect	BSC Salvador Capella	14/11/2022 online	conference
5	Joining forces to define the European Health Data Sharing Landscape for Research	EMPIRICA Carola Schulz	23/11/2022 online	meeting

6	Horizon Europe projects coordination meeting in the context of the EOSC European Partnership	EATRIS Gary Saunders	28/11/2022 online	meeting
7	Workshop EOSC4Cancer for Dutch Health-RI + cancer community	HealtI-RI /UMCG /Lygature /NKI Meijer, Boiten, Swertz et al	25/11/2022	meeting
8	Open Science Services and EOSC in Greece	CERTH	12/12/2022	other scientific collaboration
9	Annual Winter Summit AACR Project GENIE	BSC Salvador Capella	18/01/2023	conference
10	GA4GH Cancer Community	BSC/ VHIO Romina/ Xenia	09/01/2023	meeting
11	UNCAN-EOSC4Cancer meeting	BSC, DKFZ, VHIO, NKI, EUROBIOIMAGING, BBMRI, ELIXIR, Lygature	17/01/2023	collaboration with EU-funded projects
12	Preparatory meeting cBioPortal Workshop	NKI	20/01/2023	education and training event

Table 7 List of event participations until February 2023

3.5.2 Final conference

“A final open conference in M30 will showcase key project outcomes, featuring the Roadmap. EOSC4Cancer will seek links to other projects and initiatives (see section 1.2.4) to collaborate conceptually, and to use existing networks for scaled-up outreach.”

The final conference will gather the partners with interested stakeholders and synergy EU projects in Barcelona in an opportunity to learn the key results that the project came up with after 2.5 years of efforts making the cancer data available. The conference will last for two days in face-to-face roundtables and workshops to activate interactions between the various background participants on what was achieved and the road ahead of these achievements. The targeted audience will be reached through social media channels and the newsletter, including all kinds of stakeholders (see section 4.2.1), especially researchers, synergy projects, and policymakers.

The suggested agenda would ensure a high level of concrete dissemination of the project's outcomes and its strategic vision, besides discussing what possible scaled-up outreach could be looked forward to. The possible agenda is shown in the table below.

Day 1

ENVIRONMENTAL DATA FOR CANCER PREVENTION		
Speaker 1	Geo-referenced health and environmental data: lessons learned	Presentation – Q&A session
STEPPING UP CANCER SCREENING PROGRAMMES		
Speaker 2	More cancer prevention through screening optimisation	Presentation – Q&A session
A STANDARDISED AND GENERALISABLE TEMPLATES FOR THE LOCALISED CANCER CARE		
Speaker 3	How to take trustworthy cancer treatment decisions for localised colorectal cancer: Data integration	Presentation – Q&A session
Speaker 4	cBioPortal - a key to modern and data-driven cancer care?	Presentation – Q&A session
Speaker 5	Precision medicine using bioinformatic tools	Presentation – Q&A session
Panel	Deep dive: view into the future of data-driven cancer treatment	Round table

Day 2

CANCER TECHNICAL INFRASTRUCTURE FOR EOESC		
Speaker 1	Federated data spaces: fairness of data participation	Presentation – Q&A session
Speaker 2	Cancer Research – harmonised datasets and interoperability methodology	Presentation – Q&A session
Speaker 3	From fragmented data to clinical decision support systems	Presentation – Q&A session
Panel	The road ahead: scale-up opportunities	Round table

Table 8 Possible Agenda of the Final Conference

3.6 Newsletter

Many newsletter issues covering EOSC4cancer are planned for the duration of the project. It will be issued twice per month, starting in month 6, depending on the current intensity of project activity. A template for the newsletter will be created based on the project's visual identity.

Project partners will inform their existing networks of subscribers of the existence of the newsletter. Furthermore, it will be promoted to followers of the LinkedIn and Twitter accounts and a "Subscribe" button is already integrated onto the homepage of project website, in order to generate additional subscribers interested in keeping up with the project, especially for those who are not on the social media channels.

The structure of the newsletters will be based on the content of the website and social media channels but discussed more in-depth. However, the main section of the newsletters will mainly be used either to publish a project milestone (e.g., publishing a paper) or to call to action from the related stakeholders (e.g., a call for event participation).

4 Relevant structures and tools

This chapter outlines the organisational structures and concrete tools we use to carry out the communication and outreach activities on the different channels.

4.1 The virtual communication office team

In order to manage and coordinate the communication and dissemination activities of the project, a virtual Communication Office Team (vCOT) has been established. The structure of the team contains at least one representative per partner to harness all the partners perspectives in the process. The vCOT is responsible of choosing the communications topics, streamlining content production by the project and its horizontal activities. Besides organising the dissemination activities at conferences, webinars and forums are also assigned to them. It is also the central organisation meeting for social media campaigns.

The process is tracked through meetings which were part of the monthly WP6 meetings. In these calls, vCOT coordinate promotion, dissemination and communication initiatives, track partner communication efforts by reports, and take advantage of communication synergies. This way keeps all the planned events and activities, stakeholder engagement ideas and publications in the right way they were planned for.

The social media accounts of the 29 organisations in the consortium have a big number of followers. They have a combined followership of 588,173 on LinkedIn and 609,691 on Twitter (status: February 2023).

4.2 Planning tool for external visibility events

A spreadsheet used specifically for communication and dissemination reporting allows project partners to easily take stock of the situation and plan events that will increase their external visibility.

It includes several variables and is available to all project participants on the shared online project workspace. It lists the completed and upcoming tasks, along with the partners that contributed to each task. It also includes information on the intended audience, the objectives, and the results obtained utilizing Key Performance Indicators.

The vCOT utilizes this tool to organize and report on communication and dissemination during each WP6 meeting.

4.3 Social media tracking tools

As many social media activities are planned during the project, tracking tools are needed to check if these activities are achieving the aims, they were designed to. The frequent use of the tracking tools would help the consortium improving and upscaling their communication and dissemination strategy according to their results.

Therefore, two tools will be used mainly in this regard: hootsuite⁸ and trackmyhashtag⁹. The first one will be responsible of managing all the projects' social media channels. It can be used to prepare and schedule social media content, stay on top of incoming messages, and precisely analyse the results of social media campaigns. The second tool will complement the first one by tracking the metrics of any hashtag, keyword or account mentioned by the project account and showing the result on its dashboard.

4.4 Newsletter tool

The newsletter tool CleverReach¹⁰ will be used to draft, send, and manage the EOSC4cancer newsletter. Hosted in Germany, CleverReach is GDPR-compliant and has highest security standards. Its Newsletter Editor is easy to use and enables fast adaptation of contents from the website or social media campaigns to a newsletter format.

Detailed customisation functions for mailing campaigns will enable us targeting more audiences and analyse the impact.

⁸ <https://www.hootsuite.com/en-gb>

⁹ <https://www.trackmyhashtag.com/>

¹⁰ <https://www.cleverreach.com>

5 Monitoring and reporting targets

WP6 has defined different indicators enabling the monitoring and reporting of communication and outreach activities. The targets presented in the table below are aligned with the goals, target groups and channels outlined in chapters 2 and 3. The table does not yet include key performance indicators for Mastodon since the WP6 team still needs to get acquainted with the platforms typical statistics.

ID	Indicator	Method Measurement of	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
1	No. of unique visits to the EOSC4Cancer website	Web statistics	400	1000	1000
2	No. of new events published on EOSC4Cancer website	Web statistics	6	6	4
3	No. of news items published on EOSC4Cancer website	Web statistics	12	12	6
4	No. of social media campaigns	Project reporting	5	3	2
5	No. Of tweets using the hashtag #EOSC4Cancer	Twitter statistics	100	150	200
7	No. Of followers on the project's LinkedIn page	LinkedIn statistics	300	350	400
8	No. Of followers on the project's Twitter account	Twitter statistics	300	450	600
9	No. of followers on Twitter with specific relevant for cancer research	Twitter statistics	25	75	100
10	No. Of LinkedIn posts by project account	LinkedIn statistics	80	80	40
11	No. Of tweets by project account	Twitter statistics	100	200	300
12	Post/tweet impression rate by the project's account	Project reporting	8%	10%	20%
13	Post engagement rate for posts/tweets by the project's account	Twitter statistics	4%	6%	6%
14	No. of tweet engagements for tweets by the project's account	Twitter statistics	2000	2000	1000
15	No. of events (workshops, webinars, etc) organised	Project reporting	3	5	3
16	No. of papers submitted to scientific journals	Submitted papers	2	6	9
17	No. of papers submitted to international conferences	Submitted papers	4	8	7
18	No. of attendees final conference	Conference Reporting	n/a	n/a	200

Table 9 Communication and Outreach KPIs

The above key performance indicators will be verified through constant monitoring of the website and social media channels, as well as in the planning tool for external visibility events (see chapter 4.2).